

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Silvio****FIRST NAME: Dominic****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. Plagiarism is a serious academic integrity violation. There are so many ways to avoid it. Which of the following is NOT a means to avoid plagiarism?**
 - Paraphrase or quote from your sources.
 - Properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using.
 - Re-use your own previous work or imagery in new papers.¹**
 - Keep track of the sources you consult in your research.
- 2. A good academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence. Therefore, it should answer a question or task. Which of the following is NOT a component of a good academic essay?**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 6–13.

- Always do not allow time to rewrite the first draft of your essay and, then, to proofread it before turning it in.²**
- An academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources.
- It should try to present or discuss something: to develop a thesis via a set of closely related points by reasoning and evidence.
- It should have a thesis statement and an argument.
3. **According to Kate Turabian, at the core of any argumentation, there are three elements; which of the following is NOT one of the elements?**
- All arguments must have a claim.
- All arguments must have reasons that support the claim.
- All arguments must have the evidence that supports those reasons.
- All arguments must include what principle makes the reasons relevant to the claim.³**
4. **According to Kate Turabian, there are three kinds of questions that researchers ask. Which of the following is NOT one of them?**
- Conceptual questions.
- Structural questions.⁴**
- Applied questions.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 1.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, eighth edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago ; London, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 37.

⁴ Turabian, 15–17.

- Practical questions.

5. **Which of the following is NOT true about an abstract?**

- The information included in your abstract influences whether readers proceed to look at your total study.
- Abstract is the means through which other researchers, searching for studies on your topic, will be able to evaluate whether your study is useful to them.
- It is fine for the researcher to refer in the abstract to information that is not in the document.⁵**
- It is the means with which to capture potential readers' interests, thereby expanding your professional opportunities within the research community.

6. **According to Kate Turabian, a researcher is required to evaluate sources for both relevance and reliability. Which of the following is the best option for evaluating a journal article for relevance?**

- Find out whether the journal article was published by a reputable press.
- Find out whether the journal article was peer-reviewed.
- Find out whether the journal article has received good review.
- Skim the last two or three paragraphs of the introduction (or other opening section) and all of any section called Conclusion.⁶**

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, first edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc, 2008), 168.

⁶ Turabian, 28-29.

7. **The proposal is a well-thought-out written action plan that is required before embarking on writing a dissertation. Which of the following is it supposed to identify?**

- A narrowly defined and clearly written problem statement; and a purpose statement that describes how the problem will be addressed.
- Research questions that are tied to the purpose and, when answered will shed light on the problem.
- A review of the literature and relevant research to determine what is already known about the topic, and data collection and data analysis methods.
- All of the above.**⁷

8. **When searching for the right dissertation adviser, which of the following you should NOT consider?**

- Expertise.
- Chemistry.
- Accessibility and availability
- None of the above.**⁸

9. **American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II and is currently the dominant influence on world English. Which of the following is NOT a reason behind this dominant influence?**

- The international political and economic position of the U.S.
- The appeal of American popular culture on language and habits.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 17-18.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 17.

The influence of President Donald J Trump.⁹

The magnitude of the publishing industry in America.

10. **Which of the following is NOT a paradigm or school of thought?**

Pragmatism.

Critical Theory/Advocacy.

Social Constructivism, Interpretivism, or Naturalistic Inquiry.

These are all paradigms or schools of thought.¹⁰

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 27.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 8-10.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. First edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Eighth edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago; London, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.